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Novel Coordination Compounds of Lanthanides with 1-Phenyl-3-Methyl-4-(*o*-Carboxyphenylazo) Pyrazol-5-one

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THE survey of literature revealed that hardly any data is available on the stereochemical properties of lanthanide complexes with 4-arylazopyrazol-5-ones, therefore, it was thought worthwhile to study the spectral and magnetic behaviour of some lanthanide complexes. The present note describes the isolation and characterization of La(III), Pr(III), Nd(III), Gd(III) and Dy(III) chelates of 1-phenyl-3-methyl-4-(*o*-carboxyphenylazo) pyrazol-5-one on the basis of chemical analysis, magnetic and ir spectral studies.

Experimental

Glass apparatus with standard joints and all the chemicals of reagent grade were used. The ligand was prepared¹ by the gradual addition of diazotised

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solution of *o*-amino benzoic acid (0.025 mole) to an ice cold solution of 1-phenyl-3-methylpyrazol-5-one (0.025 mole) in acetone (50 ml) containing sodium acetate with constant stirring and maintaining the temperature 0.5°. Excess of water was added to the reaction mixture, stirred for half an hour and left overnight. The orange solid was separated by filtration, dried in vacuum dessicator and crystallized from glacial acetic acid. The purity of the ligand was checked by TLC. The m.p. of the ligand was found to be 270°.

Preparation of lanthanide complexes: Aqueous solutions of lanthanide(III) chlorides (Johnson and Matheu) were mixed to acetonic solution of the ligand (M : L, 1 : 2). The pH (~8) of the reaction mixture was adjusted with aqueous sodium hydroxide (1M) and the mixture then refluxed for an hour. The product obtained on cooling was filtered, washed successively with acetonitrile and finally with acetone.

Elemental analysis and other physical measurements have been recorded as reported earlier².

Results and Discussion

All the complexes are fairly stable coloured solids and can be stored without any change for a long time. The purity of these complexes was checked by TLC. The molecular weight determinations in boiling chloroform shows them to be monomers. This further gets support by their ir spectral studies. The molar conductance values (116.2-120.6 mhos) in DMF at the concentration 10⁻³ M show that these are uni-univalent electrolytes. The analytical results show that these complexes correspond to the general formula [Ln(C₁₇H₁₃N₄O₃)₂.2H₂O]Cl where Ln=La(III), Pr(III), Nd(III), Gd(III) or Dy(III).

All coordination compounds under study except La(III)-complex are paramagnetic while latter is diamagnetic because of the presence of unpaired electrons in 4f subshells, which are shielded by 5s, p and d orbitals and hence it is very difficult for the ligands to attack the inner 4f electron. Therefore, the magnetic moments of the complexes should be affected to a less extent as compared to that of the metal salt itself³. There is a slight variation in experimental magnetic moment values (Table 1) which may be due to the thermal population of excited states whose degenerate levels have been split by the crystal field^{4,5}.

Infrared spectral studies: In the ir spectra of the lanthanide complexes under study, the shifting of the frequencies of >C=O (1625 cm⁻¹) and -N=N- (1565 cm⁻¹) to lower region, 1600 and 1545 cm⁻¹ respectively indicates the involvement of

TABLE 1

Complex*	Colour	Chemical analysis**				μ_{eff} Experimental values B.M.	μ_{eff}^{***} Theoretical values B.M.
		%C	%H	%N	%M		
(a)	canary yellow	47.97 (47.73)	3.29 (3.33)	13.17 (13.00)	16.93 (16.00)	0.25	—
(b)	yellow	47.86 (47.62)	3.28 (3.32)	13.13 (13.06)	16.52 (16.18)	3.21	3.62
(c)	yellow	47.68 (47.43)	3.27 (3.31)	13.08 (13.01)	16.85 (16.53)	3.51	3.68
(d)	yellow	47.96 (47.72)	3.22 (3.30)	12.89 (12.79)	18.10 (17.73)	7.86	7.94
(e)	yellow	46.69 (46.45)	3.20 (3.31)	12.81 (12.74)	18.56 (18.15)	10.89	10.64

* (a) $[\text{La}(\text{C}_{17}\text{H}_{12}\text{N}_4\text{O}_3)_2 \cdot 2\text{H}_2\text{O}]\text{Cl}$, (b) $[\text{Pr}(\text{C}_{17}\text{H}_{12}\text{N}_4\text{O}_3)_2 \cdot 2\text{H}_2\text{O}]\text{Cl}$, (c) $[\text{Nd}(\text{C}_{17}\text{H}_{12}\text{N}_4\text{O}_3)_2 \cdot 2\text{H}_2\text{O}]\text{Cl}$,
 (d) $[\text{Gd}(\text{C}_{17}\text{H}_{12}\text{N}_4\text{O}_3)_2 \cdot 2\text{H}_2\text{O}]\text{Cl}$, (e) $[\text{Dy}(\text{C}_{17}\text{H}_{12}\text{N}_4\text{O}_3)_2 \cdot 2\text{H}_2\text{O}]\text{Cl}$.

** Theoretical values are in bracket.

*** Using Van-Vleck values.

these two groups in complexation. The disappearance of $-\text{COOH}$ group band (2600 cm^{-1}) and the appearance of new breathing frequencies at 1350 cm^{-1} and 800 cm^{-1} due to symmetric stretching and bending mode of OCO frequencies respectively indicate the participation of the $-\text{COOH}$ group in complexation. Further, after the complexation the $\text{O}-\text{H}$ frequency disappeared indicating there by the loss of hydrogen ion and coordination of oxygen of the carbonyl group in the formation of complexes. Coordination of water molecules is indicated by the appearance of bands at $3300\text{--}3350\text{ cm}^{-1}$ in the complexes.

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Extraction and Spectrophotometric Determination of Vanadium(V) with N-Hydroxy-N-m-tolyl-N'-(2-methyl-5-chloro)phenyl-p-toluamide Hydrochloride in Presence of Salicylic, Anthranilic and Phthalic Acids

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N-HYDROXY-N-m-tolyl-N'-(2-methyl-5-chloro)-phenyl-p-toluamide hydrochloride, a newly synthesised bidentate chelating agent possessing

the recently explored hydroxyamide functional grouping, I^{1-5} , reacts with vanadium(V) in presence of various carboxylic acids to form coloured complexes. The present work

deals with the solvent extraction and simultaneous spectrophotometric determination of microgram quantities of vanadium(V) as mixed ligand complex with N-hydroxy-N-m-tolyl-N'-(2-methyl-5-chloro)-phenyl-p-toluamide hydrochloride (HTMCPTH) and six carboxylic acids viz. salicylic, acetylsalicylic (aspirin), sulfosalicylic, anthranilic, N-phenyl-anthranilic and phthalic. The method presented here is simple, rapid, sensitive and reasonably selective.

Experimental

Reagents and apparatus: N-Hydroxy-N-m-tolyl-N'-(2-methyl-5-chloro)phenyl-p-toluamide hydrochloride (HTMCPTH) was prepared by condensing N-(2-methyl-5-chloro)phenyl-p-toluimidoyl chloride and N-m-tolylhydroxylamine in ether according to the method of Deb and Mishra. m.p.-175; yield, 65% (Found: C, 66.10; H, 5.46; N, 6.80%. Calc. for $\text{C}_{23}\text{H}_{22}\text{N}_2\text{OCl}_2$: C, 65.53; H, 5.48; N, 6.98%). The compound possesses infrared spectral bands characteristics of hydroxyamides^{6,7}.

0.015M solution of HTMCPTH and 0.06M solution of carboxylic acid were prepared in chloroform. A stock solution of vanadium(V) was prepared by dissolving ammonium metavanadate (0.52 g) in double distilled water (1:1) and the solution standardised volumetrically⁸.

The absorption spectra were recorded with a Carl-Zeiss Specord spectrophotometer and absorbance measurements were made with an ECIL GS-865 spectrophotometer equipped with 1-cm matched